

AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA TALABALARNING MUSTAQIL ISHLARINI TASHKIL ETISH

ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT WORK OF STUDENTS IN AN INFORMATION EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ СТУДЕНТОВ В ИНФОРМАЦИОННОЙ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЕ

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada axborot-talim muhitida talabalar mustaqil ishlarini samarali tashkil etish shart-sharoitlari, asosiy omillari haqida so'z yuritilgan. Shuningdek, axborot talim muhitida talabalar mustaqil ishlarini tashkil qilishda pedagoging boshqaruv funksiyalari, mustaqil ishlash jarayonida duch keladigan muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari ham yoritilgan.

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the general conditions and conditions for the effective organization of students' independent work in the information-educational environment. Also, the functions of pedagogical management in the organization of independent work of students in the information educational environment, the problems encountered in the process of independent work and ways to overcome these are also considered.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются основные условия и факторы эффективной организации самостоятельной работы студентов в информационно-образовательной среде. Также рассматриваются функции педагогического менеджмента при организации самостоятельной работы студентов в информационно-образовательной среде, проблемы, возникающие в процессе самостоятельной работы, и пути их преодоления.

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Internet ijtimoiy xizmatlari, axborot talim muhiti, ochiq talim resurslari, axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, paradigma

KEYWORDS

Internet social services, information learning environment, open learning resources, information and communication technologies, paradigm

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

интернет социальные услуги, информационная среда обучения, открытые учебные ресурсы, парадигма

INTRODUCTION

In the educational process, students develop the skills of independent work with literature. In the previous chapter we paid attention to the self-education of the learning and developing student. All the above tasks (questions and assignments) given to them serve to stimulate the students' thinking. The main thing is that the student creates himself, acquiring the ability to understand scientific and life problems.

Teaching students to learn independently is one of the important issues in the methodology of teaching psychology.

Psychology and other academic subjects included in its composition are studied in Ukhmina in the same way as other humanities subjects. But it has its own characteristics and cannot be taken into account. Its goals, problems, content.

If the goal of teaching psychology is to understand a person and correctly interact with him, regardless of who he is, then knowledge of the theoretical (from the book) rules will help the future specialist in a higher educational institution. the ultimate goal of education, but only a means to achieve it. The main goal is the ability to know the psychology of existing people.

With the help of developmental education, the student develops theoretical thinking skills, and through this, memorization of educational material from a book, loss of rote memorization, organization of the student's independent educational activities with the right approach.

MAIN PART

This means that when reading literature and listening to lectures, students always compare people's life behavior with their personal thoughts and feelings, critically analyze them and evaluate them from a new scientific point of view.

This means that in the material being studied, the student does not memorize theory, but develops thinking, which helps him learn better by analyzing life events with its help. This is the only way to master psychology as a science,

like any other science in general. However, psychology has advantages over many other disciplines. In particular, the area of practical application of scientific knowledge, as well as developments at hand as practical material, etc.

In order for students to achieve their stated goals, the teacher needs to resolve the following issues.

1. Formation of a motivating factor in the student for in-depth study of science, and through this he must decide the following. "Why do I need psychology?", "Why should I study psychology?" If it was for a "diploma", a "reputation", then the reason for the student learning science is to explain that it still needs to be improved.

This question is the first and most important task that a teacher should know. How to solve this? Explain to the student when, where and why he personally needs to know the psychology of people in life, and so on. The goal of revealing the subject and tasks of psychology in the field of science is realized in the first lecture. In the lecture, psychology is important for a person's life, as a person grows up, he needs a group of people, so he should be interested in knowing psychology for his future activities. In the process of learning science, the explanation of the need deepens and, as a result, becomes an interest in psychology. In this educational activity, the practical meaning is based on an understanding of the personal content of acquiring scientific psychological knowledge, and interest in learning actually increases.

In order to assimilate the knowledge gained from lectures and books, it is necessary to explain to students that they should be compared with real psychological phenomena, trying to explain them on the basis of psychological knowledge. Examples from the literature analyzed by the teacher during lectures, and practical assignments (psychological and pedagogical issues) discussed in practical classes, seminars, or practical assignments that make up the content of written tests in psychology will help solve this problem. This comparison of

scientific rules with life events means teaching people psychology. Studying the events of daily life from a psychological point of view means understanding and studying it in order to build the right relationship with a person in any situation. Leadership is about teaching and nurturing obedience to another person while creating a psychological environment that is conducive to relationships.

When studying literature independently, the following motto should be a constant instruction for the student, calling to action. It is necessary to write down all the conclusions obtained as a result of psychological analysis (research) of life events. To take such notes in traditional teaching (in schools and universities), you often have to write notes, consisting of copying and writing down what is already in the book. But if an idea comes from a book, it needs to be interpreted immediately. The student must write down personal thoughts that reflect his/her practical understanding of the written rules. This means that his understanding of science is independent of reality.

When solving these problems, the student must not only listen to the lecture, but also not only read the book, understanding its content, he must be able to understand its content, conduct psychological analysis, evaluate people's behavior based on his knowledge, learn from his scientific knowledge ready for use in everyday practice. Teaching at a university depends on the proper organization of students' independent work between classes. In order for independent learning not to turn into just another temporary activity (the student begins reading books six months before the session), it should help him turn this work into a permanent system.

It is known that the study of science requires a holistic approach, independence in terms of content and execution, and not artificial compulsion to solve a problem. All elements of the learning structure, such as the study of individual issues, access to some private and formal reports (for example, "reporting" on the timely completion of a test) are all naturally

connected with each other, which does not allow one to master the content of science, which cannot be fully mastered separately from each other in some system conditions. Even if you can remember something, you still cannot know it deeply and cannot serve as a scientific manager of human social behavior.

If a student begins to solve a particular problem (for example, to complete the work of writing an essay), but has not yet mastered the scientific foundations for fully solving this problem, he will use scientific knowledge that allows him to understand the behavior of existing people to achieve the main goal, he creates artificial statements for himself on the way to acquiring knowledge. Therefore, the environment is not student reports on individual forms of the curriculum, but a step-by-step comprehensive study of the subject, simultaneously mastering it and forcing it to solve all individual educational issues. This is dialectics: a student masters science by solving a specific problem, and learning becomes capable of correctly solving all subsequent educational (theoretical and practical) problems. This can only be achieved with the help of an integrated and systematic approach to teaching natural sciences, in particular, to organizing independent learning for students. How can a student implement an integrated approach to independent work? The main thing is that the student relies on the information received in lectures, when reading textbooks and other literature. He must compare what he read from one source with information received from another source, confirm and clarify the knowledge gained. They, in turn, need to be compared with real mental phenomena that can still be observed in life, in people, including themselves. Thus, in the lecture there is a phenomenon of transition from theoretical literature to practice. At the same time, knowledge that is not in the student's mind is adopted, that is, the process of assimilation occurs. Knowledge in the scientific literature can be considered acquired only when the student

learns to use the knowledge acquired by performing practical analytical operations to study human psychology.

Thus, mastering science by a student means not only a good knowledge of its content, but also the ability to apply this knowledge in practical situations. Independent learning as a system has its own structure. It is important for the student to fully use all the elements of this structure. It should also be borne in mind that not every student can turn to the teacher for advice. Experience shows that students do not even come to meet with teachers on duty for consultations. In a serious situation, when it is necessary to understand the complex theoretical issue of mastering educational material, the student primarily relies on the ability to build his own educational activities. But no matter what happens, the freshman still can't read. This helps him to use some techniques and ways of working so that he can quickly acquire independent learning skills. To consider these methods, we will divide them into independent works:

- reading lecture notes;
- reading, translation and synthesis of educational and scientific literature;
- preparation for exams (tests).

Reading lecture notes has several purposes:

- firstly, remember what was discussed in the lectures;
- second, fill the student's work with life examples and ideas that strengthen and group the understanding of what was heard in lectures;
- thirdly, read information from the textbook, which cannot fully reveal the short meaning, but to which students should pay special attention when reading some documents and literature.

In this case, lecture notes serve as a kind of guide and guideline for their further work. Helps to better and more fully understand issues that are only shown in lectures, but not covered. Here it is important to choose real-life methods to explain this or that psychological phenomenon, since the thought process itself, when choosing

an example that corresponds to the student's real observations, the mental activity of mastering a given existing problem or topic in accordance with life leads to the implementation of the theory in practice. This is the first attempt.

A textbook is the main and important type of educational literature. It organizes the material in chronological order of achievements in a given subject and in a language understandable to the student.

The textbook as the main type of educational literature has the following features.

Firstly, the textbook consists of all the basic materials of the scientific discipline in an abbreviated form. All the basic concepts and categories of this science with the necessary expressions (distinctions) are included; if necessary, a brief history of the formation of the concept in science is given. Often this is the logic of the development of science itself, and the understanding of the situation depends on its content from the point of view of the categories that form a common basis.

CONCLUSION

All this, of course, is true for any teacher, but nevertheless it is useful to think again about the role of the teacher in his work and in the teaching of the student. It is recognized that the roles of the teacher and the student are different in terms of, and sometimes in contrast to, the process. Many students overestimate the textbook. They consider him the only source of knowledge. That's why they don't write down lectures, they believe in the book that they have everything to pass the exam. Other students believe that the main source of learning is lecture materials, that is, lectures supplemented and developed by information from other textbooks. They do not look elsewhere for scientific truth. In particular, they do not use the recommended scientific literature, which is considered the primary source of scientific psychological knowledge. They make the mistake of considering a textbook to be a sufficient resource for a subject as long as they can pass an exam based on a high grade in the textbook.

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